

HEALTH PROBLEMS OF OIL INDUSTRY WORKERS WHILE WORKING IN THE SELECTED OIL INDUSTRIES

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(MS Received: 18.05.2023; MS Revised:22.06.2023; MS Accepted:23.06.2023)

MS 3054

(RESEARCH PAPER IN COMMUNITY SCIENCE,)

Abstract

The study was conducted in thirty renowned oil industries located in the selected cities of Marathawada region in Maharashtra state (Parbhani, Hingoli, Aurangabad, Jalna and Nanded). These oil industries were involved in expelling oil from cotton seed for the last 10-12 years. It was seen that majority of workers working in the selected oil industries were female. Majority of male & female workers were in 32-40 yrs. age group having average weight of male workers were between 50-62 kg and weight of female workers up to 49 kg. Regarding experience of workers working in oil industries it was observed that majority of male workers (63.63%) were working in the oil industry since 9-12 yrs., while majority of female workers (67.79%) employed in the industry since 5-8 yrs. It is found that male workers experienced very severe pain in shoulder, neck and finger while female workers experienced very severe pain in shoulder and fingers. It was observed that age and experience of male workers were having correlation with frequency score of finger pain and vision problem, whereas weight of the female workers were having correlation with frequency score of pain in shoulder, knee, leg, neck and back pain. It was also noticed that asthma, allergy, suffocation, nausea, increased blood pressure and increased heart beats were the common health hazards of majority of the male workers while working in oil industry, whereas headache, suffocation, nausea and increased blood pressure were the common complaints of female workers working in oil industry. Statistical analysis showed significant difference between frequency scores of health hazards of male and female workers.

Age, weight and experience of male workers were having correlation with frequency score of increased blood pressure, where as age and weight of female workers were having correlation with frequency score of cough, increased blood pressure and increased heart beats while working in oil industry.

Key words: Musculoskeletal, health hazards, problems

Introduction

Workplace hazards remain a significant concern for workers in the oil and gas industry, where workers are continuously exposed to different forms of occupational hazards. It is believed that the oil and gas working environment is one of the most dangerous working settings. However, the industry poses various occupational risks due to numerous process activities (Eyayo, 2014). Globally, 2.9 billion workers are exposed in their workplace to risk threats. There are also two million deaths annually attributed to occupational diseases and injuries, and 4% of gross domestic product (GDP) - is lost due to occupational illnesses and injuries (Meswani, 2008).

In the 2000 World Health Organization survey, it was concluded that 37% of workers suffer from back pain, 16% from hearing illness, 13% from chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, 11% from asthma, 10% from trauma, 10% from lung cancer, and 2% from leukaemia are responsible for occupational hazards globally. It is still estimated by the International Labour Organization (ILO) that 2 million workers die per year from work-related occupational diseases. However, the rate of work-related accidents and injuries varies across countries, depending on the level of industrial development. In particular, developing countries continue to record tremendous losses in work-related occupational accidents, diseases more than the developed countries.

The importance of occupational health is often overlooked and people tend to equate occupational illness with industrialization and huge factories in urban areas. This narrow view hampered the development of occupational health in developing countries. While at work, people face a variety of hazards almost as numerous as the different types of work, including chemicals, biological agents and adverse ergonomic conditions etc. WHO's programme on workers health is concerned with the control of occupational health risks, the protection and promotion of the working populations and the humanization of work (Berenice, 1998). Also work has its positive effect as increased productivity, higher quality work and increased workforce morale among others are indices of workers well being and to some extent job satisfaction.

Objective :

To find out the effect of noise levels in selected industries on health of the workers.

Materials & Methods

The study was conducted in thirty renowned oil industries located in the selected cities of Marathawada region in Maharashtra state (Parbhani, Hingoli, Aurangabad, Jalna and Nanded). These oil industries were involved in expelling oil from cotton seed for the last 10-12 years. All the selected oil industries were established by small and medium entrepreneurs.

Musculoskeletal problems of workers working in oil industry

Incidence of musculoskeletal problems of workers of oil industry was identified by using body map. The problems at shoulder, knee, vision problem, leg, neck, back, hands and fingers was recorded after completion of work inside the oil industry. The intensity of pain in above noted parts of body was recorded by using five point scale indicating the intensity as very severe, severe, moderately severe, light and very light pain with 5, 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively

Health hazards experienced by workers of the selected oil industry

Frequency of health hazards experienced by workers of selected oil industries was collected on three point scale as always, some times and never with respective score of 3, 2 and 1 respectively.

Correlation Co-efficient

Correlation co-efficient was calculated for describing the degree of correlation between dependent and independent variables in the study were age, weight, and BMI of selected high school going student.

Results:

It is evident from the table that among the workers working in the oil industries majority (51.75%) workers were females, whereas 48.24 per cent of them were male. Majority (54.54%) of male workers working in the oil industries were in the age group of 32-48 yrs., followed by age above 49 yrs. (30.90%) and up to 31 yrs (14.54%), whereas majority (69.49%) of female workers working in the oil industries were

in the age group of 32-48 yrs, followed by up to 31 yrs. age group (20.03%) and above 49 yrs. age group (8.47%).

With reference to weight of the workers it was found that majority of (76.33%) male workers working in oil industries were having body weight ranged between 50-62 kg, while 20 per cent and 3.63 per cent workers having body weight ranged between above 63 kg and up to 49 kg respectively, whereas majority of female workers were having body weight up to 49 kg (74.57%) followed by weight of female workers ranged between 50-62 kg (25.42%).

Musculoskeletal problems and intensity of problems experienced by workers working in selected oil industries were recorded on body map & presented in table 1. It is clear from the table that majority of male workers (83.63%) were having very severe pain in shoulder followed by pain in fingers (54.54%). Equal percentage (18.18%) of male workers were having very severe pain in hands and knees. Equal percentages (12.72%) of male workers were also having very severe leg, neck and back pain. Less percentage (3.63%) of female workers were having very severe vision problem.

With respect to severe pain, it was noted that maximum percentage (38.18%) of male workers were having severe pain in neck. Equal percentages of male workers (36.36%) were having pain in knee, hand and fingers, while 34.54 per cent male workers were having pain in legs. Very less percentage of male workers were having severe problems of vision (9.09%), shoulder pain (5.45%) and back pain (3.63%).

Majority (83.63%) of workers were having moderate pain in back followed by equal percentage (45.45%) of workers were having moderate knee and hand pain, whereas equal percentages (41.81%) of them were having moderate leg and neck pain. Very fewer percentages of male workers experienced moderate finger pain and vision problems (9.09% and 5.63% respectively).

With regards to light pain, 27.27 per cent male workers having light vision problem followed by neck pain (7.27%) and equal percentage (5.45%) were having shoulder and leg pain. Equal percentage (5.45%) of male workers experienced very light pain in shoulder and leg, while only 3.63 per cent of male workers experienced very light vision problem.

With respect to female workers it was noticed that majority (88.13%) of the female workers were having very severe pain in shoulder followed by pain in finger (40.67%), whereas very less percentage (8.47%) of female workers were having severe pain in knees, vision problem, pain in legs, neck, back and hands. As regards severe pain it was found that equal percentage (40.67%) female workers were experienced it in hands and finger, where as severe pain in vision, shoulder and leg were experienced by 13.55 per cent, 11.86 per cent and 10.16 per cent female workers respectively.

Regarding moderate pain experienced by female workers while working in oil industry it was found that majority (88.13%) of them experienced back pain followed by leg pain (64.40%), and equal percentage (50.84%) experienced pain in knee and hands, whereas neck pain, vision problem and finger pain were experienced moderately by 49.12 per cent, 42.37 per cent and 18.64 per cent female workers respectively. Maximum percentage (35.58%) of female workers experienced light vision problem and very few percent (5.04% and 1.69%) of them experienced light neck and knee pain while working in oil industry.

Significantly highest score for body parts indicated that male workers experienced very severe pain in shoulder (4.56), neck (4.56) and finger (4.45), followed by moderate pain in knee (3.72) leg (3.43) and back (3.29), while female workers experienced very severe pain in shoulder (4.81) and fingers (4.22), followed by moderate to severe pain in knee (3.54), neck (3.49), leg (3.44) and back (3.20). Statistical analysis with one way analysis of variance indicated significant difference in different body parts and frequency scores of musculoskeletal problems

of both the male and female workers (Male $F=4.00^{**}$ and Female $F=6.58^{**}$).

Correlation between selected independent variables and frequency of musculoskeletal problems experienced by workers working in selected oil industries is presented in table 2. It was found that age of the male worker is positively correlated with frequency of finger pain (0.250^{*}), indicates that as age of male workers increased there was an increase in finger pain. It may be because finger muscles are finer muscles so that flexibility of muscles decreases.

Body weight of female workers showed positive correlation with frequency of shoulder pain (0.637^{**}), knee pain (0.269^{*}), leg pain (0.345^{**}), neck pain (0.287^{*}), back pain (0.272^{*}) and hand pain (0.345^{**}). This indicates that as the body weight of female workers increased there was increase in frequencies of pain in shoulder, knee, leg, neck, back and hand. It may be due to increased body weight, there is deposition of fat on different body parts like shoulder, knee, leg, neck, back and hands. So the muscles gets stiffen and while doing movement there is pain in these body parts.

Experience of male workers was found a positive correlation with vision problem (0.340^{**}) which indicates that as the experience of male workers increased while working in oil industry the problem of vision increased. It can be stated that as the experience was increased age also increased and due to increased age sight of the person becomes weaken. Health hazards and frequency of experience by workers while working in selected oil industry is shown in table 3. It is evident from the table that cent percent of male workers were always suffering from asthma, allergy, suffocation, nausea, increased blood pressure and increased heart beats; whereas headache, vomiting and cough were the health hazards experienced by 96.38 per cent, 87.27 per cent and 83.63 per cent of male workers respectively.

With regards to female workers cent percent of them were suffering from headache, suffocation, nausea and increased blood pressure, while more than 80 per cent of female workers expressed that they always suffered with cough, asthma, allergy, vomiting and increased heart beats.

Mean average scores for health hazards and frequencies of experience for male workers while working in oil industries indicated higher values of frequencies for suffocation (2.83), increased blood pressure (2.65), allergy (2.38), asthma (2.21) and nausea (2.03). Mean average score were lower for headache (1.96), vomiting (1.92), cough (1.87) and dampness (1.34).

Mean average scores for health hazards and frequencies of experience for female workers while working in oil industries showed higher values of frequencies for allergy (2.98), suffocation (2.88) increased blood pressure (2.27) headache (2.01) and nausea (2.00), whereas lower values of frequencies of mean average scores were noticed for asthma (1.98), cough (1.93), vomiting (1.91), increased heart beats (1.89) and dampness (1.30) while working in oil industries.

Correlation between selected independent variables and frequency of health hazards experienced by workers while working in selected oil industries is presented in table 4. It is found that age of male worker was positively correlated with frequency of blood pressure (0.426^{**}) increased while working in oil industry. It may be due to continuous exposure to high noise level blood pressure increases, indicating that with increase in age frequency of the blood pressure was increased. The results are inline with the results of Bhardwaj and Sinha (2016) showed that ambient industrial noise causes a statistical rise in blood pressure of workers, while age of the female workers was positively correlated with frequency of cough (0.259^{*}) indicating that with increase in age of female workers frequency of the cough was increased. It may be because of the increased age immunity of the person decreases and also due to the harmful gases releasing out from the processing in the oil industry. As far as weight is concerned it was observed that there was a

significant correlation of weight with frequency of increased blood pressure of male (0.289*) and female (0.609**) workers while working in oil industry. It was also noticed that weight of female workers was positively correlated with frequency of increased heart beats (0.344**). Experience of male workers was found positively correlated with frequency of increased blood pressure (0.364**), while working in oil industry.

Conclusion

It is concluded that male workers experienced very severe pain in shoulder, neck and finger while female workers experienced very severe pain in shoulder and fingers. It was observed that age and experience of male workers were having correlation with frequency of finger pain and vision problem, whereas weight of the female workers were having correlation with frequencies of pain in shoulder, knee, leg, neck and back pain.

It was also observed that asthma, allergy, suffocation, nausea, increased blood pressure and increased heart beats were the common health hazards of majority of the male workers while working in oil industry, whereas headache, suffocation, nausea and increased blood pressure were the common complaints of female workers working in oil industry. Statistical analysis showed significant difference between frequency scores of health hazards of male and female workers.

Age, weight and experience of male workers were having correlation with frequency of increased blood pressure, where as age and weight of female workers were having correlation with frequency of cough, increased blood pressure and increased heart beats while working in oil industry.

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Table 1. Musculoskeletal problems and intensity of problems experienced by workers working in selected oil industries

Sr. No.	Body parts	Percentage and frequencies											
		Mean Score	Male N = 55					Female N = 59					
			Very severe (5)	Severe (4)	Moderate (3)	Light (2)	Very light (1)	Mean Score	Very severe (5)	Severe (4)	Moderate (3)	Light (2)	Very light (1)
1	Shoulder pain	4.56	46 (83.63)	3 (5.45)	0	3 (5.45)	3 (5.45)	4.81	52 (88.13)	7 (11.86)	0	0	0
2	Knee pain	3.72	10 (18.18)	20 (36.36)	25 (45.45)	0	0	3.54	5 (8.47)	23 (38.98)	30 (50.84)	1 (1.69)	0
3	Vision problem	2.81	2 (3.63)	5 (9.09)	31 (5.63)	15 (27.27)	2 (3.63)	2.94	5 (8.47)	8 (13.55)	25 (42.37)	21 (35.58)	0
4	Leg pain	3.43	7 (12.72)	19 (34.54)	23 (41.81)	3 (5.45)	3 (5.45)	3.44	5 (8.47)	16 (10.16)	38 (64.40)	0	0
5	Neck pain	4.56	7 (12.72)	21 (38.18)	23 (41.81)	4 (7.27)	0	3.49	5 (8.47)	22 (37.28)	29 (49.12)	3 (5.04)	0
6	Back pain	3.29	7 (12.72)	2 (3.63)	46 (83.63)	0	0	3.20	5 (8.47)	2 (3.38)	52 (88.13)	0	0
7	Hand pain	3.00	10 (18.18)	20 (36.36)	25 (45.45)	0	0	2.76	5 (8.47)	24 (40.67)	30 (50.84)	0	0
8	Finger pain	4.45	30 (54.54)	20 (36.36)	5 (9.09)	0	0	4.22	24 (40.67)	24 (40.67)	11 (18.64)	0	0
		F Value = 4.00**, SE = 1.86 CD = 6.92					F Value = 6.58**, SE = 2.34 CD = 8.71						

Figures in parenthesis indicates percentages ** = Highly Significant at 1 % level

Table 2. Correlation between selected independent variables and frequency of musculoskeletal problems experienced by workers working in the selected oil industries

Sr. No.	Body parts	Age		Weight		Experience	
		Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female
1	Shoulder pain	-0.085NS	0.164 NS	0.045 NS	0.637**	0.166 NS	-0.040 NS
2	Knee pain	0.067 NS	0.050 NS	0.171 NS	0.269*	0.006 NS	0.054 NS
3	Vision problem	0.230 NS	-0.138 NS	0.130 NS	0.020 NS	0.340**	-0.128 NS
4	Leg pain	0.061 NS	-0.021 NS	-0.104 NS	0.345**	0.088 NS	0.039 NS
5	Neck pain	0.078 NS	-0.059 NS	-0.017 NS	0.287*	0.247 NS	0.006 NS
6	Back pain	0.087 NS	-0.165 NS	-0.103 NS	0.272*	0.122 NS	0.024 NS
7	Pain in hands	0.020 NS	0.021 NS	0.084 NS	0.345**	0.131 NS	0.039 NS
8	Finger pain	0.250 *	0.237 NS	0.139 NS	0.111 NS	0.223 NS	0.214 NS

NS: Not Significant , *- Significant at 5% level , ** - Highly Significant at 1 % level

Table 3. Health hazards and frequency of experience by workers while working in selected oil industry

Sr. No.	Health Hazards	Frequency of Health Hazards									
		Male					Female				
		Total N = 55	Mean Average score	Always	Some time	Never	Total N = 59	Mean Average score	Always	Some time	Never
1	Dampness	19 (34.54)	1.34	0	19 (34.54)	36 (65.45)	18 (30.50)	1.30	0	18 (30.50)	41 (69.49)
2	Cough	46 (83.63)	1.87	2 (3.63)	44 (80.00)	9 (16.36)	52 (88.13)	1.93	3 (5.08)	49 (83.05)	7 (11.86)
3	Asthma	55 (100)	2.21	12 (21.81)	43 (78.18)	0	52 (88.13)	1.98	6 (10.16)	46 (77.96)	7 (11.86)
4	Allergy	55 (100)	2.38	21 (38.18)	34 (61.81)	0	51 (86.44)	2.98	14 (23.72)	39 (66.10)	6 (10.16)
5	Headache	53 (96.38)	1.96	0	53 (96.36)	2 (3.63)	59 (100)	2.01	1 (1.69)	58 (98.13)	0
6	Suffocation	55 (100)	2.83	46 (83.63)	9 (16.36)	0	59 (100)	2.88	52 (88.13)	7 (13.55)	0
7	Vomiting	48 (87.27)	1.92	2 (3.63)	46 (83.63)	8 (14.54)	53 (89.83)	1.91	1(1.69)	52 (88.13)	6 (10.16)
8	Nausea	55 (100)	2.03	2 (3.63)	53 (96.36)	0	59 (100)	2.00	0	59 (100)	0
9	Increased blood pressure	55 (100)	2.65	36 (65.45)	19 (34.54)	0	59 (100)	2.27	16 (27.11)	43 (72.88)	0
10	Increased heart beats	55 (100)	2.30	17 (30.90)	38 (69.09)	0	53 (89.83)	1.89	0	53(89.83)	6 (10.16)
F Value = 11.73**, SE = 3.13 CD = 12.64						F Value = 16.84**, SE = 3.56 CD = 16.81					

Figures in parenthesis indicates percentages ** = Highly Significant at 1 % level

Table 4. Correlation between selected independent variables and frequency of health hazards experienced by workers while working in the selected oil industries

Sr. No.	Body parts	Age		Weight		Experience	
		Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female
1	Dampness	-0.230 NS	0.076 NS	0.077 NS	-0.041 NS	-0.235 NS	-0.142 NS
2	Cough	0.071 NS	0.259*	0.176 NS	-0.086 NS	0.037 NS	0.026 NS
3	Asthma	-0.037 NS	0.057 NS	-0.018 NS	-0.263 NS	-0.021 NS	0.057 NS
4	Allergy	-0.084 NS	-0.172 NS	-0.045 NS	0.069 NS	-0.125 NS	-0.184 NS
5	Headache	0.052 NS	-0.056 NS	0.187 NS	-0.068 NS	0.054 NS	-0.024 NS
6	Suffocation	0.083 NS	0.164 NS	-0.004 NS	0.126	-0.176 NS	0.061 NS
7	Vomiting	-0.081 NS	0.202 NS	-0.006 NS	-0.199 NS	-0.173 NS	0.078 NS
8	Nausea	0.052 NS	0.110 NS	0.163 NS	-0.047 NS	0.054 NS	0.031 NS
9	Increased blood pressure	0.426**	0.181 NS	0.289*	0.609**	0.364**	-0.111 NS
10	Increased heart beats	0.070 NS	0.059 NS	0.072 NS	0.344*	0.003 NS	0.007 NS

NS- Not Significant , *- Significant at 5% level , ** - Significant at 1 % level